

ISic0227

I.Sicily inscription 0227

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dis Manib(us)
2. Trebonia C(ai) · f(ilia) Modia
3. vixit · ann(is) XI m(ensibus) III
4. C(aius) Trebonius Zmaragdus
5. et Modia Hesione
6. piissimae filiae

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini with slight changes based on the photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285305

EDR 127531

EDCS 10900662

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 152

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 139

Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici Romani. Berlin. At VIII 707

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